

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight B297
Date: 22 June 2007
Take Off 10:10:09
Landing: 15:26:36
Flight 5h16m27s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Nouakchott - Dakar

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM1	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	CCM2	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
5	Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Mission scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
8	Mission scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
9	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
10	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	Leeds University

Flight Track:

B297 Track 22-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B297
 Date: 22 June 2007
 Project: Gerbil
 Location: Nouakchott / Dakar

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094802		GIN	0.10 kft	078	running
094821		CGPS	0.10 kft	078	B297cgps.log
094834		INU	0.10 kft	078	to navigate
094902		DRS	0.10 kft	078	checked
100459		Heimann	0.10 kft	078	cal 13
101009		T/O	0.09 kft	037	
101009	103635	Profile 1	0.43 - 24.0 kft	038	start at t/o
101009		psap	0.90 kft	063	flow on at T/O
101020		heimann	1.2 kft	128	open at T/O
101254		Video	1.8 kft	203	#1 ffc, #2 dfc
101437		TWC	3.2 kft	221	power cycled
103635	113834	Run 1.1	24.0 kft	202	
103730		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	203	
104137		bbr	24.0 kft	203	retract
104811		Sonde 2	24.0 kft	202	
105806		heimann	24.0 kft	210	cal 08
110542		Sonde 3	24.0 kft	212	
111454		Sonde 4	24.0 kft	212	
112750		Sonde 5	24.0 kft	212	
113705		JW	24.0 kft	213	zero
113807		!	24.0 kft	213	all JW prior to this point u/s
114348		Video	24.0 kft	044	#1ffc, #2dfc end
114418	121125	Profile 2	24.0 - 0.12 kft	044	
114451		video	23.6 kft	044	#3 ffc, #4 dfc star
114503		bbr	23.4 kft	044	extend
115327		P2	15.0 kft	033	P2 interrupted
115532		P2	15.0 kft	221	P2 resumed
120743		psap	3.3 kft	212	flow off
121407	121803	Profile 3	0.12 kft	219	
121142		!	0.46 kft	210	manoeuvre
121803	134335	Run 2.1	4.0 kft	030	
121830		bbr	4.0 kft	031	retract
121844		psap	4.1 kft	031	flow on
124359		Heimann	4.0 kft	036	cal 11
124835		psap	4.0 kft	038	filter change
130610		Ubbr	4.0 kft	036	reset
131643		Ubbr	4.0 kft	035	reset
132833		Video	4.0 kft	026	#3 & #4 end
132913		Video	4.0 kft	026	#5 ffc, #6 dfc start
133309		Video	4.0 kft	027	#6 now set to ufc
134530	134843	Profile 4	4.1 - 8.0 kft	196	
134843	135752	Run 3.1	8.0 kft	192	
135752	140700	Profile 5	8.0 - 15.0 kft	201	
140100		bbr	11.3 kft	202	extend
140146		P5	12.0 kft	201	interrupt
140354		P5	12.0 kft	009	resumed
140701	141618	Run 4.1	15.0 kft	025	
140756		bbr	15.0 kft	025	retract
141619	142318	Profile 6	15.0 - 22.0 kft	025	
141649		bbr	15.3 kft	025	extend
142537	143844	Run 5.1	22.0 - 21.0 kft	031	
142552		bbr	21.1 kft	193	retract
143342		Sonde 6	21.1 kft	200	
144051	150528	Profile 7	21.1 - 0.21 kft	031	
144238		bbr	19.7 kft	036	extend
144353		heimann	18.5 kft	035	cal 10
145227		P7	10.1 kft	028	interrupt
145419		P7	10.1 kft	195	resumed
145720		Video	7.5 kft	192	#7 ffc, #8 ufc start

150528	150731	Run 6.1	0.21 - 0.22 kft	204
150542		bbr	0.20 kft	205 retracted
150832	151003	Orbit 1	0.65 - 0.61 kft	238 300M
151024		heimann	1.1 kft	297 cal 11
152636		Land	0.19 kft	350 Dakar

B297 Track 22-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

Gerbils: Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Intercomparison of Longwave and Shortwave radiation.

Flight No: B297a

Date: 22nd June 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ and remote sensing measurements of Saharan dust and the associated effect on solar and terrestrial radiation.

Location:

Over ocean areas between Nouakchott and Bimut and Narat.

Weather:

High loadings of dust aerosols. Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/wet-nephelometer combination

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

Flight pattern:

1. If clear from cloud, perform a pirouette of ~3minutes duration before take off.
2. Take off from Nouakchott at 10:00Z.
3. Perform a profile ascent to Bimut to arrive at FL200 (25mins, T=25mins).
4. Launch sonde.
5. Perform SLR at FL200 towards from Bimut direct to Narat launching sondes every 10 minutes (35mins, T=60mins).
6. Reciprocal turn followed by a profile descent to an intermediate level (suggest FL140) (10mins, T=70mins).
7. SLR at intermediate flight level (suggest FL140) from Narat to Bimut (30mins, T=100mins).
8. Reciprocal turn followed by a profile descent to an intermediate level (suggest F70) (10mins, T=110mins).
9. SLR at intermediate flight level (suggest FL70) from Bimut to Narat (35mins, T=145mins).
10. Reciprocal turn followed by a profile descent to MPA (10mins, T=155mins).
11. SLR at MPA (100ft) from Narat towards Bimut (60mins, T=215mins).
12. Profile ascent towards Nouakchott (25mins, T=240mins).
13. Recover to Nouakchott (20mins, T=260mins).

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B297

Date: 22nd June 2007

Sortie Objectives: To investigate the in-situ and radiative effects of dust storms in conjunction with the GERB/SEVIRI satellite instruments.

Operating area: Oceanic areas off the coast of W. African countries of Mauritania and Senegal.

Weather: Hazy conditions with significant dust. Variable cloud. Alto stratus capping the dust layer to the north of the operating region and Sc capping the marine boundary layer to the south of Dakar.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take-off, a profile ascent was performed to FL240 above the dust layer. A long SLR was then performed at this altitude to a point to the south of the operating region (approximately 11.5N, 19.7W). A series of 4 sondes were launched at this altitude. At the beginning of this run As topped the dust layer (at about FL200), then we were clear from cloud in the Dakar region, and then low level Sc capping the marine boundary built up to the south of the region. A broken profile descent was then performed to 100ft before popping up above the Sc to FL40 which was approximately 1000ft above the tops of the Sc. A long SLR was performed heading in a northerly direction towards Dakar where SWS and ARIES were in zenith viewing mode and should have some very good measurements of the radiative effect of mineral dust (as should the SHIMS instrument). The Sc thinned to nothing some 50miles south of Dakar – the lower BBRs clearly showed the influence of the Dakar peninsula. The SLR was continued to the north at FL40, where some higher level As started to affect the BBRs. A reciprocal turn and profile were made to FL70 where in-situ sampling of the dust was performed. A reciprocal turn and a profile ascent to FL150 was then performed followed by a SLR for radiation and in-situ sampling purposes. A reciprocal turn and profile ascent was then made to FL220, back towards Dakar with ARIES and SWS nadir viewing and a further sonde was dropped. A broken profile descent was then performed to 100ft, followed by a 2 minute run for ARIES to measure the SST. A single 45degree banked orbit was then performed, before recovery to Dakar.

Summary: A very successful flight in terms of radiation measurements. It will be particularly useful to analyse:

- 1) The effect of dust on the SWS and ARIES down-welling radiances from measurements below the dust. SHIMS data should also be analysed.
- 2) The effect of dust on the upwelling and downwelling radiances in the area just north of Dakar, perhaps extending slightly to the south (nice influence of Dakar on the lower BBR). SHIMS data should also be analysed.

Problems:

PCASP did not function after the first profile ascent – it was later found that the motor had failed.

CO shows some unusual profiles which warrants further investigation.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

GERBIL

Flight No **B...297...**

Date **22 June 07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Dusty 6/8 ACU / EAS.
					Visibility ~ 1km.
					Operating between waypoints INIRO & TAROT.
					Failed ERF tests ∴ have to stay within 1 hour of Dakar. Have to cut short of TAROT.
	PIA	0			Start profile from surface.
					Very dust at surface → 1800ft 1,800ft → low level dust storm.
					Clear slot 3,000ft.
10:10:06s		5000ft			Dust above, some very thin but extensive cloud.
					Neph reached $3000 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in the lowest dust layer at 1500ft
10:30					Some cloud below
					Free from cloud above.
10:35					ARIES & SWS to zenith

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.297**.....
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 Date **22 June 07**

 Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:36:35	End P1 / P1	FL240			Some cloud below at very start of run.
10:37:30					
10:40:00		FL240			SWS + ARIES to nadir. Free from cloud now Still affecting BBRs.
10:42:00		FL240			Now no cloud effect on BBRs.
10:48:11					Sonde #2 BBRs showing 110 Wm^{-2} → DRE = 60 Wm^{-2} .
10:56:					BBRs show increase → Over-clouded a bit of land (Dakar peninsula). No No use of BBR data
					10:50:00 → 11:00:00 No cloud at low level below 3/8 Cu below → cloud below
11:05					
11:14:54		FL240			Sonde #3, 3/8 Cu below
11:05:42		FL240			Sonde #4.
11:27:50		FL240			Sonde #5.
11:38:34	End P1	FL240			End run. 3/8 Cu at low level
11:44:18	Start P2	FL240			Broken descent to FL150
11:53					SWS Zenith looking.
	Start P2	FL150			
11:55:32	Restart P2	FL150			5/8 Cu below

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.297** Date 22/06/07 Name Jim HAYWOOD Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Cloud Tops at FL30.
					Profile Bottom clouds FL20..
					Sea state 5 - some whitecaps
	End P2	100ft			Clouds thin Sc.
12:14:07	Start P3	100ft			Wind 8ms ⁻¹ .
					Cloud base ~ 2000ft.
					Cloud top ~ 3000ft.
12:18:03	End P3 Start R2.1	4000ft			End Pro/St Run.
					Lots 7/8 Sc below
					during this run.
13:00		4000ft			Sc thinning here to 3/8
13:05		4000ft			Sc now 1/8
13:06					Free from low level cloud.
13:19:30		4000ft			Over the coast
13:21:30					Spike in lower BBRs
					as over Dakar.
					15.41N, 17.03W →
					Upper pyranometers & SWS
					dropping - will check
					few Ci on upper cameras.
13:40					Some Ci
13:43:35	End R2.1	4000ft			End R2.1
					Cut short due to Ci above
					- free from cloud to south.
13:45:30	Start P4	4000ft			To FL80

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Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B 297** Date 22/06/07 Name Jim Haywood Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:48:43	End P4 St R3.1	FL80 →	192		V. v. little Ci above.
13:57:52	End P5 PS	FL80 ↑			Profile climb
14:01:46	Int P5	FL120 →			Reciprocal turn
14:03:54	Restart P5	FL120 ↑			Profile climb recommenced.
14:06:58	St R4.1	FL150 →			Towards Bikis.
14:16:19	End Run SEP6	FL150 ↑			
14:17:00					Some Ci/As above.
14:21					Above cloud. Top at FL200. Clear above.
14:26:18	End P6	FL210			
14:25:17	St R5.1	FL210			8/8 AS/ACU below, capping top of dust layer. Free from cloud below now
14:32:30					
14:33:42					Sonde #6. BBR data → 105 W m ⁻² 14:32:30 → 14:39:00 = 55 W m ⁻² DRE
14:38:44	End R5.1	FL210			
14:40:51	St P7	FL210 ↓			
14:49					Back under cloud bits
14:52:75		FL100 →			Break profile. // top top gear. MBC at 3000ft. 130 m ⁻¹ × 10 ⁻⁶ scat at 1800ft.

11) 0
bumped
SEA 29°.

- ① MPA D+40 → Bikis
- ② FL70 Bikis → D+40
- ③ FL140 D+40 → Bikis
- ④ FL220 Bikis → D+40
- ⑤ Profile Descent to MPA
- ⑥ Orbits
- ⑦ Recover.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B297

Date : 22/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air. Data incorrect.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
TDLAS	None

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 297

Date: 22/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:10:00	Motor	Failed														Start P1 from Takeoff	
10:13:15			28	10	1											FL020	
10:14:26				5	1											FL030	
10:15:30				10	1											FL040	
10:16:31			29	20	3											FL050	
10:17:34				40	8											FL060	
10:18:35			30	40	6											FL070	
10:19:36				30	3											FL080	
10:20:44				20	5											FL090	
10:21:43			31	30	5											FL100	
10:22:50				70	10											FL110	
10:23:48			32	70	10											FL120	
10:25:00				70	10											FL130	
10:25:59				60	8											FL140	
10:26:58				50	3											FL150	
10:27:59			33	40	5											FL160	
10:28:55				40	7											FL170	
10:29:58				30	3											FL180	
10:30:55				20	3											FL190	
10:32:02				1												FL200	
10:33:10				1												FL210	
10:34:10				1												FL220	
10:35:22				1												FL230	
10:36:36				1												End of P1 & Start Run 1 @ FL240	
10:40:00				1													
10:45:00																	
10:50:00				1													
10:55:00				1													
11:00:00			34	1													
11:05:00																	
11:10:00				1													
11:15:00																	
11:20:00																	
11:25:00				1	1												
11:30:00				1													
11:35:00			35	1													
11:38:22																End of Run 1	
11:44:16																Start P2 from FL240	
11:45:30				1	1											FL230	
11:46:28																FL220	
11:47:29																FL210	
11:48:27				2	1											FL200	
11:49:32				3	1											FL190	
11:50:33				15	10											FL180	
11:51:25				90	10											FL170	
11:52:24				100	10											FL160	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 297

Date: 22/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:53:30			36	100	10											FL150	
11:56:55			39	120	10											FL140	
11:57:55			40	110	20											FL130	
11:58:58			42	100	10											FL120	
11:59:54			43	110	20											FL110	
12:01:10			45	80	10											FL100	
12:02:13				80	10											FL090	
12:03:10			47	80	10											FL080	
12:04:10			48	50	8											FL070	
12:05:12			49	40	10											FL060	
12:06:11				40	10											FL050	
12:07:07			50	40	10											FL040	
12:07:56				20	8											FL030	
12:08:50			88	100	10											FL020	
12:09:45				80	8											FL010	
12:11:27			89	60	2											End of P2 @ 100'	
12:14:03			90	50	5											Start P3 from 100'	
12:15:22			91	70	10											FL010	
12:16:17			140	1000	3000											FL020	
12:17:15			388	10	10											FL030	
12:18:03																End of P3 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL040	
12:20:00			390	30	7												
12:22:00				20	1												
12:24:00			391	20	3												
12:26:00			392	20	10												
12:28:00				20	10												
12:30:00			393	40	10												
12:32:00			394	40	8												
12:34:00			395	40	10												
12:36:00			396	40	8												
12:38:00			397	40	5												
12:40:00			398	40	5												
12:42:00			399	40	5												
12:44:00			400	40	10												
12:46:00			402	40	10												
12:48:00			403	40	8												
12:50:00			404	40	7												
12:52:00			405	30	10												
12:54:00			406	20	8												
12:56:00			407	20	5												
12:58:00			408	20	5												
13:00:00			409	30	5												
13:02:00			410	30	5												
13:04:00			411	20	3												
13:06:00			412	30	7												
13:08:00			414	30	6												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 297

Date: 22/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:10:00			415	20	3												
13:12:00			416	30	5												
13:14:00			418	30	3												
13:16:00			419	20	4												
13:18:00			420	20	5												
13:20:00			421	20	5												
13:22:00			422	15	5												
13:24:00			423	20	3												
13:26:00			425	20	3												
13:28:00			426	20	3												
13:30:00			427	20	3												
13:32:00			428	15	3												
13:34:00			429	20	3												
13:36:00			430	20	2												
13:38:00			431	15	3												
13:40:00			432	15	5												
13:42:00			433	15	3												
13:43:40																End of Run 2.1	
13:45:23																Start P4 from FL040	
13:46:17			434	20	3											FL050	
13:47:07			435	30	3											FL060	
13:48:02			436	30	3											FL070	
13:48:43				30	3											End of P4 & Start Run 3.1FL080	
13:50:00			437	40	3												
13:52:00			438	40	3												
13:54:00			439	40	6												
13:56:00			440	40	6												
13:57:52																End of Run 3.1 & Start P5 from FL080	
13:58:55				50	7											FL090	
13:59:47			441	80	8											FL100	
14:00:46				80	8											FL110	
14:01:50				30	3											FL120	
14:05:09			442	20	3											FL130	
14:06:06				15	2											FL140	
14:07:01				20	1											End of P5 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL150	
14:08:00				20	1												
14:10:00			443	20	1												
14:12:00				20	2												
14:14:00				20	2												
14:16:00				30	4												
14:16:19																End of Run 4.1 & Start P6 from FL150	
14:17:35			444	30	3											FL160	
14:18:39				60	3											FL170	
14:19:28				70	5											FL180	
14:20:28			447	1000	1000	10	800									FL190	
14:21:25			464	5												FL200	

B297_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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09:58:16.02 --- - - - -
09:58:16.02 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:58:16.02 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:58:16.02 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B297
09:58:16.02 --- - - - -
09:58:22.50 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:58:30.59 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:58:32.69 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:59:39.49 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:59:43.83 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
09:59:45.50 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
10:00:14.77 --- - - - -
10:00:14.77 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
10:00:14.77 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
10:00:14.77 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B297
10:00:14.77 --- - - - -
10:00:25.67 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:00:29.99 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:00:32.25 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
10:01:54.35 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:02:15.19 SWS - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
10:02:18.05 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
10:02:21.20 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
10:02:24.08 USH - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
10:02:26.77 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
10:02:29.05 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
10:02:32.31 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:02:32.31 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:02:32.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:02:37.24 USH - - - - Idling
10:02:38.22 SWS - - - - Idling
10:02:40.98 LSH - - - - Idling
10:02:43.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:02:43.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:02:43.15 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:02:50.27 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
10:02:54.11 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
10:02:57.73 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
10:03:05.61 SWS - - - - Idling
10:03:07.18 USH - - - - Idling
10:03:09.10 LSH - - - - Idling
10:07:05.13 --- - - - - *** taxiing out...data start
10:07:17.32 --- - - - - *** sws to 90 aft for take off
10:07:26.15 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:07:26.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:07:26.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:07:33.18 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
10:07:37.02 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:07:40.44 SWS - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
10:11:41.94 SWS 6F - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
10:11:50.30 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
10:11:53.05 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:00.99 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:12:04.65 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
10:12:11.24 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:14.97 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:18.12 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:12:18.92 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:12:19.17 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:12:22.05 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
10:13:29.93 --- - - - - *** sws to 10F for climb
10:14:22.30 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:14:29.75 SWS - - 150 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 150ms.
10:14:33.00 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
10:14:34.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

10:14:57.22	---	-	-	-	*** clear low level dust but cloud above
10:16:41.57	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
10:16:44.79	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:52.75	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:34.69	---	-	-	-	*** cirrus above
10:27:58.96	USH	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:28:06.66	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:06.72	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:06.81	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:08.99	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:10.59	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:14.79	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:54.34	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:34:00.29	SWS	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
10:34:05.07	SWS	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
10:34:09.92	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
10:34:18.82	USH	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
10:34:24.19	USH	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
10:34:34.25	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:34.26	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:34.40	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:38.39	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:38.69	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:42.59	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:18.98	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:35:24.66	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
10:35:27.86	SWS	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
10:35:30.08	SWS	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
10:35:33.73	SWS	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:35:36.31	SWS	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
10:35:43.97	LSH	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:35:48.10	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:48.12	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:48.63	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:52.75	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:56.03	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:35:56.57	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:03.20	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:36:04.99	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:12.93	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:54.46	---	-	-	-	*** start r1 at FL240
10:40:19.48	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:40:25.48	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
10:40:31.24	SWS	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
10:40:33.53	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:38.67	LSH	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:40:40.96	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:41.46	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:48.89	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:51.98	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:41:56.59	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:42:04.52	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:16.83	SWS	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
10:57:20.02	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:26.14	LSH	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
10:57:28.06	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:28.06	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:36.20	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:14.64	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
11:03:22.75	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
11:03:26.85	LSH	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
11:03:29.57	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:29.61	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:29.80	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:03:34.06	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:37.72	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:03:37.98	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:31.11	---	-	-	-	*** little bits cloud below
11:08:08.11	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.

11:08:11.90	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
11:08:14.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:18.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:54.52	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:08:56.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:04.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:14:25.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** still over flying shallow CU below
11:38:29.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R1
11:44:26.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** p2 start
11:53:08.42	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
11:53:16.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:16.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:16.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:20.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:20.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:24.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:35.73	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
11:53:40.83	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
11:53:57.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:05.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:58:06.38	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:58:10.34	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:58:13.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:58:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:04.71	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
12:00:06.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:00:08.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:00:31.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 10500ft
12:08:24.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloudin
12:08:53.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** shallow cu at 2100ft
12:11:50.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile at 100ft
12:12:05.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile ascent
12:12:11.45	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:12:16.12	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
12:12:19.29	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
12:12:23.43	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
12:12:33.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:12:34.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:12:36.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:12:37.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
12:14:27.49	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 75ms.
12:14:31.06	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
12:14:34.41	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
12:14:36.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:36.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:36.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:14:38.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:41.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:14:44.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:33.43	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
12:16:39.21	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
12:16:40.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:41.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:19.82	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
12:17:24.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:32.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:28.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** start r2.1 at 4000ft
12:19:25.56	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
12:19:29.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:19:36.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:18.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** flying above the shallow Cu
12:34:08.54	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:34:11.62	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
12:34:13.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:34:14.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:16.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:34:17.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:25.14	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.

12:54:27.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:54:28.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:01.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** solar zenith angle is 9.14 degrees
13:22:31.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** momentary spike a minute ago just as we passed over land at Dakar
13:23:11.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** suspect upwelling radiation being bounced back from dust layer above
13:23:43.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** from dust layer above
13:30:14.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:14.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:14.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:30:15.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:18.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:30:22.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:09.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:09.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:09.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:10.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:14.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:17.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:44.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R2.1
13:45:50.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** start profile 4 climb
13:48:51.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile and start 3.1 at fl080
13:49:05.53	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 25ms.
13:49:10.30	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
13:49:13.75	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
13:49:17.99	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
13:49:21.25	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
13:49:24.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:24.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:24.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:26.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:28.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:32.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:40.07	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
13:49:44.88	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
13:49:49.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:56.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:58:14.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r3.1 start P5
14:01:55.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** interrupt profile
14:04:36.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** restart profile
14:07:05.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profel and start r6.1 at FL150
14:07:17.35	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:07:21.58	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 150ms.
14:07:25.25	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
14:07:29.45	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
14:07:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
14:07:42.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:42.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:42.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:46.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:50.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:50.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:06.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS to 175R
14:16:34.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run and start P6 to FL220
14:23:16.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P
14:23:36.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P6 at FL220
14:24:35.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** dropping
14:24:42.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** to FL210
14:25:50.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** start R5.1 at FL210
14:26:25.51	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
14:26:30.50	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:26:33.17	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
14:26:40.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:41.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:41.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:45.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:46.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:48.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:32:33.65	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:32:39.70	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
14:32:43.65	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:32:47.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:47.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:47.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:52.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:57.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:57.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:41.30	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
14:37:46.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:55.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:59.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R5.1
14:40:57.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P7
14:41:57.78	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:42:07.19	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
14:42:26.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 3F for descent
14:47:52.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:52.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:52.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:56.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:00.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:00.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:51:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
14:51:32.01	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 25ms.
14:51:34.43	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
14:51:36.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:51:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:39.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** int profile at FL100
14:54:29.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** restart profile sescent
14:55:08.28	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:55:15.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:15.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:15.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:17.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:19.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:23.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:32.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P7 Start R6.1 at 100ft
15:05:43.55	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
15:05:48.91	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
15:05:54.25	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 75ms.
15:05:57.56	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
15:06:00.91	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:06:04.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:04.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:04.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:08.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:10.12	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:06:10.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:12.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:34.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
15:07:45.13	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 10ms.
15:07:48.40	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 50ms.
15:07:59.67	SWS	-	-	-	25	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 25ms.
15:08:05.06	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
15:08:08.10	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:08:13.73	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 25ms.
15:08:16.03	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 25ms to 50ms.
15:08:19.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:19.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:19.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:20.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:23.20	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 10ms.
15:08:24.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:26.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:26.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:27.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:27.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:31.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```
15:08:36.03 --- - - - - *** start orbit 1
15:08:46.97 --- - - - - *** 45deg aob right hand turn
15:10:06.02 --- - - - - *** end orbit
15:11:21.83 --- - - - - *** end science for approach to Dakar.
```

ARIES flight log

Flight: B297

page 1 of 4

Date:

Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: ~~Nouakchott~~ ^{Dakar} ~~Nouakchott~~ to Niamey

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 24	0. kupa	1x60	CH	C	71	45	Script 1 (1x60 CBB, 1x60 HBB)
09 30							Turned scanner off hoping CBB will cool (low)
10:10	TAKE OFF						
10 35 10	FL210?	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Skill climbing?
10 36 55	R1-1	360x1	Z	O	70	41	Clear above, cloud + dust below
10 40 12		1x60	CH	C	71	41	Shutter closing during cal - ditch!
10 41 19		"	CH	C	71	41	
10 42 35		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, no apparent cloud. Clear above
10 45 36		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 46 57		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below surface obscured ^{Hint of colour, no feature}
10 49 51		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 51 21		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below. Surface obscured.
10 54 24		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 55 45		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below. Some small clouds.
10 58 50		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 00 06		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 03 09		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 04 29		360x1	N	C	71	42	Dust + patchy cloud below
11 07 34		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 08 49		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust + patchy cloud below
11 11 53		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 13 11		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 16 19		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 17 41		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust + patchy cloud below
11 20 45		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 22 34		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust + patchy cloud below
11 25 35		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 26 52		360x1	N	C	71	41	- - -
11 30 08		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 31 24		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 34 32		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13297

page 2 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A:

B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 3545		360x1	N	C	71	41	Aborted near end at end of run.
11 3827		1x60	CH	C	70	41	
	P2L P5A						
12 1706	P21	1x60	CH	C	71	41	cal in climb.
12 1834	4000ft	360x1	Z	O	70	41	
12 2142		120x1	N	C	71	41	Broken cloud below, surface ^{early} visible
12 2247		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 2423		360x1	Z	O	71	41	Dust above
12 2735		120x1	N	C	71	41	
12 2840		1x60	CH	C	71	42	← Might have messed up cal
12 2935		"	CH	C	71	41	
12 3047		360x1	Z	O	70	41	Shutter opening at start of view
12 3359		120x1	N	C	71	41	
12 3508		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 3620		360x1	Z	O	70	41	Shutter!
12 3935		120x1	N	C	71	42	
12 4038		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 4159		360x1	Z	O	70	42	Dust above
12 4511		120x1	N	C	71	42	Cloud below
12 4617		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 4733		360x1	Z	O	70	41	
12 5050		120x1	N	C	71	42	
12 5154		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 5348		360x1	Z	O	70	41	
12 5632		60x1	N	C			
12 5707		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 5826		360x1	Z	O	70	42	Dust above, cloud below.
13 0142		60x1	N	C	71	42	
13 0215		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 0337		360x1	Z	O	70	42	
13 0653		60x1	N	C	71	43	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13297

page 3 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
13 07 32		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 08 54	4000fl	360x1	Z	O	71	43	
13 12 03		60x1	N	C	71	43	
13 12 39		1x60	CH	C	71	43	
13 13 54		360x1	Z	O	70	43	Dust above, no cloud below
13 17 07		60x1	N	C	71	44	CSA definitely creeping up
13 17 47		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
13 19 00		360x1	Z	O	70	44	
13 22 14		60x1	N	C	71	44	
13 22 54		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
13 24 08		360x1	Z	O	71	44	
13 27 20		60x1	N	C	71	44	
13 27 55		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
13 29 14		360x1	Z	C	70	44	
13 32 28		60x1	N	C	71	45	?
13 33 10		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
13 34 23		360x1	Z	O	71	45	
13 37 33		100x1	N	C	71	45	
13 38 27		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
13 39 44		360x1	Z	O	71	44	13:41:20 cloud overhead
13 43 34		1x60	CH	C	71	45	
	R3.1						
13 48 37	FL080	1x60	CH	C	71	45	
13 49 49		360x1	Z	O	70	44	Clear above
13 53 05		100x1	N	C	71	44	
13 53 58		1x60	CH	C	71	44	
13 55 11		240x1	Z	O	70	44	Shutter! Opening from 15% onwards
13 58 01		1x60	CH	C	71	43	Cal in climb.
	R4.1						
13 06 53	FL150	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
14 08 10		360	N	C	71	41	

Flight:

B297

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:48:01

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:49:20

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B297

Date: 22 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. pcasp u/s
4. pcasp 2 u/s

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 22/6/07

Flight No: B297

Pre-Flighter: JT

Item	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A.
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	TOTAL WATER NOT FILLED YET
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nezovor	Checked and OFF	
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Press. Cell gas still high 517
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☒	FWVS	Set up	N/A
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	V. NOISY
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FILLED YET
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☒	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	☒	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	☒	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	N/A
27	☒	CGPS	Set up	SWITCHED ON - NOT LOGGING
28	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	☒	NO PH ZORO		ANDY NELSON PERFORMING
	☐			
	☐			
External Checks overleaf				➔

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	stripped
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N/A
41	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	N/A
42	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	N/A
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	☒	ICEX applied		
45	☒	Traps empty (weekly only)		

B297 Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

EAA051_20070622_0915.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 0915 UTC

EEA041_20070622_0915.jpg

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 0915 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1015.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1015 UTC

EEA041_20070622_1030.jpg

EAA051_20070622_1115.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1115 UTC

EEA041_20070622_1115.jpg

EEA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1115 UTC

EEA041_20070622_1215.jpg

EEO41 MSG dat RGB 22 Jun 2007 1215 UTC

SDDI-20070622-1200-BNW-09-IR_108-05-600.jpg

MET9 22 JUN 2007 1200 BNW IR_108 5

EAA041_20070622_1415.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1415 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1415.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1415 UTC

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B297:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras
1 x Down/Upward Facing Cameras
1 x Upward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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